

Factors Influencing the Community to Cockfight and Challenges of Police Officers in Suppressing Illegal Cockfighting in the Philippines

Bill Clark G. Liday¹, Mark L. Bitos², Jefferson E. Usin³, Alvin J. Sumampong⁴,
Jenny C. Cano^{5,*}, Jiffrey B. Saguran⁶, Arturo A. Tagle⁷, Melina G. Gabon⁸

^{1,2,3,6,7,8}College of Criminal Justice Education, St. Paul University Surigao, Surigao City, Philippines

⁴College of Education, Culture & Arts, Saint Paul University Surigao, Surigao City, Philippines

⁵College of Engineering, Saint Paul University Surigao, Surigao City, Philippines

*Corresponding Author: jenny.cano@spus.edu.ph

Abstract Cockfighting, referred to locally as “sabong”, is a customary activity that enjoys significant popularity and social acceptance in the Philippines. Nevertheless, it is subject to government oversight, and regulations have been established to guarantee its conduct in a humane and secure manner. This study focused on the factors influencing the community to cockfight and the challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfighting in the municipality of Anao-aon, Surigao del Norte, Philippines. Quantitative-descriptive research design using survey method was used. Participants were 80 residents and 41 police officers chosen purposefully. Researchers-made instrument was utilized which was subjected to validation by experts in the field of criminal justice, language, and research. Mean, standard deviation, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson correlation were employed to analyze the data after satisfying the normality assumption. Results showed that the residents played cockfight as a source of income and livelihood which provides easy to earn and somehow improve their quality of life. Despite the activity was insufficient to suffice their needs and not all gambling players perceived that gambling activity was a form of investment that could double or triple the money, the cockfight gambling still provides genuine happiness to the residents for this aroused their interest to apply strategies to win. This game changed their negative moods to positive for the actual cockfight gave them pleasure. The activity helped the residents to think critically applying the best strategies to win. Every player had stories of winning and losing the game which served as a lesson learned that built their character and boosted their confidence to invest and continue the game. Moreover, the mountainous location of the gambling venue, lack of cooperation among the residents, billable charges, and political support were the prevailing challenges encountered by the police officers in suppressing illegal cockfight gambling.

Keywords *cockfight, economic factors, entertainment factors, learning factors, challenges, criminology*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Cockfighting is one of the oldest spectator sports in the world. It functioned as entertainment for the royal family and remains quite popular today, despite the fact that it is banned and deemed cruel in many nations. Cockfighting is considered as a method to earn a lot of money rapidly in a nation where poverty is rampant. People invest a lot of money into breeding the birds and have a good chance of winning rich if their roosters consistently win battles. During cockfights amongst their roosters, affluent folks sometimes wager vehicles and mansions. [1]

In the Philippines, cockfighting has been and still is a popular, traditionary and customary form of recreation and industrial entertainment during legal holidays, local fiestas, agricultural, commercial and industrial fairs, carnivals or expositions. Whereas, by reason of the aforementioned meaning and connotation of cockfighting in relation to Filipino customs and traditions, it should neither be exploited as an object of commercialism or business enterprises, nor made a tool of uncontrolled gambling, but more as a vehicle for the preservation and perpetuation of native Filipino heritage and thereby enhance our national identity [2]. Cockfighting, locally termed “sabong”, is a popular pastime in the country, where both illegal and legal occur.

It is a blood sport in which two roosters specifically bred for aggression are placed beak to beak in a small ring and encouraged to fight to the death.

Besides being cruel to animals, cockfighting is closely connected to other crimes such as gambling, drugs and acts of violence. Illegal weapons have also been found at cockfights because of the large amounts of cash present, and law enforcement raids across the country have established that cockfights are well attended by gang members, further encouraging violence and illegal drug use. To avoid suspicion, organizers regularly move the events to new locations. Despite the unsettling facts, cockfights often inspire a party-like atmosphere in which entire families gather, including children. Another case reported, the Northern Samar provincial government has issued a stern warning against illegal cockfighting after four aficionados turned positive for coronavirus disease 2019 (Philippine News Agency). Meanwhile, the Philippine National Police has arrested seven persons engaged in illegal cockfighting in its week-long operations in the towns of Catarman, Mondragon, San Isidro, and San Jose in Northern Samar [3].

Accordingly, the Philippine National Police spokesperson Brig. Gen. Bernard Banac admitted that they have been receiving reports of illegal cockfighting events being secretly held during the quarantine. Banac said that this can be considered as a violation of Republic Act 11332 or the Mandatory Reporting of Notifiable Diseases and Health Events of Public Health Concern Act as well as local ordinances prohibiting mass gatherings during the quarantine period. [4]

San Francisco, previously Ana-aon, is a coastal municipality in Surigao del Norte's province. The municipality covers 53.71 square kilometers (20.74 square miles), accounting for 2.75 percent of the entire area of Surigao del Norte. The population is 15,347 according to the 2020 Census. As observed, people tend to cockfight for the reasons that the location of the place is remote and there are many venues to cockfight that might difficult for the police officers to locate and capture. The activity is continuous because there are many reasons that they cockfight. These reasons lead or may capsulized into to three factors namely economic or livelihood, entertainment, and learning experience.

The current situation captured the interests of the researchers to find out the level of influence of the different factors to the residents to cockfight and determine the extent of challenges of Police Officers in suppressing illegal cockfight so as to come up better ways to cover up the conduct of cockfighting in the community.

1.2 Objectives

This study specifically addressed the following questions:

- 1.2.1 What is the demographic profile of the residents in terms of age, years in playing cockfight, estimated monthly income, monthly frequency of playing cockfight, number of cock or rooster, and average money spent for cockfight?
- 1.2.2 What is the demographic profile of the police officers in terms of age, sex, length of service, and designation?
- 1.2.3 What is the level of influence of cockfighting to the residents in terms of economic factor, entertainment factor, and learning factor?
- 1.2.4 What is the extent of challenges encountered by police officers in suppressing illegal cockfight?
- 1.2.5 Is there a significant difference on the level of the factors influencing the residents' cockfighting when grouped according to profile?
- 1.2.6 Is there a significant difference on the level of the challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfighting when grouped according to profile?
- 1.2.7 Is there a significant relationship on the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight and the level of the challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfight?

1.3 Literature Review

Cockfighting in the Philippines has been a part of life for thousands of years. The spectacle of fighting animals has long been a part of human history. From bullfighting all the way down to cockfighting, the fighting has existed across many cultures in some form. In many countries, however, animal fighting, particularly cockfighting has been banned due to its violent and cruel nature. Despite this controversial standing, for many,

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it's still seen as a competition just like any other. In the Philippines, sabong – cockfighting – is a way of life. Cockfighting has been around for hundreds of years. When Ferdinand Magellan arrived in 1512, it was already a roaring spectacle. As such, the culture around it is deeply entrenched in Philippine life, particularly in the provinces, where cockfighting is part of the daily scrabble for income. [5]

Cockfighting has climbed to a whole new level and it is a booming Billion-Dollar Industry in the Philippines that has not only captured the heart of the entire nation, but also the world at large. Popularly known as Sabong, cockfighting isn't just legal in the Philippines, it's also a national obsession. Based on the report made by [6], the Joint Task Force Covid Shield ordered police officers to intensify the campaign against illegal cockfighting operations, including the online streaming of these activities. And to intensify intelligence-gathering and coordination especially with barangay officials following the conduct of recent operations which led to the arrest of violators, including government officials.

Economic Factor Influencing to Cockfight

The most fundamental notion of human life is that there is contact between people, which is accompanied by the presence of an inter-human purpose in meeting their basic requirements. The interactions that have been built can be seen with various patterns and motives, one of which is in the activity of fighting chickens. In addition, with the existence of cockfighting as an alternative solution to the community's economy, namely to become a business field for rooster sellers, food sellers or stalls around the location of cockfighting gambling, arena owners, as well as gambling players themselves. [7]

Accordingly, the total Game fowl, good cash profits might be achieved routinely from the betting system employed in the sport (to the article released in 2015 titled Earn Cash from the Cockfighting's Betting System). Because of this, many people routinely participate in sports to increase their income. Because of the betting system, many people have turned to cockfighting as their main source of revenue despite the fact that they are neither handlers nor gaffers and do not own any game birds. Additionally, in a nation where poverty is rampant, cockfighting is perceived as a quick method to make a lot of money. People invest a lot of money in raising the birds, and if their roosters consistently triumph in competitions, there is a good probability that they will become wealthy. [8]

Cockpit operator Atong Ang claims that the virtualization of combat has only increased demand. He asserts that many Filipinos engage in cockfighting as a pastime, a kind of entertainment, and an escape from the stresses of everyday life. All socioeconomic groups, even the wealthiest, favor it. One of them is Chavit Singson, a member of the House of Representatives, as well as several businessmen and politicians, including the former president of the Philippines, Joseph Estrada. So, it should come as no surprise that cockfighting generates a \$1 billion industry, according to the Games and Amusements Board, the government agency in charge of overseeing it.

The government also plans to impose a tax on internet service provider earnings. Others rely solely on it for their income. like 32-year-old veterinarian Bryan Fuentes, who is known for combating cockroaches. Despite not being a veterinarian by trade, he is qualified to work in the field. For each game cock he heals after a match, he is paid 500 pesos (\$10). He often sees at least four patients per day. Ang, the cockpit operator, is anxious to highlight the fact that his business employs Filipinos. Around 385,000 people are employed in the sector, including those working on poultry farms and feed warehouses, according to industry statistics. There are a whopping 20 million game birds in the country. [9]

In addition, the article, the reasons why you should bet on cockfighting (2018) the profiting from cockfight wagering is simple. Through betting on cockfights, it is possible to quickly amass a fortune. There is nothing better than additional income, and cockfighting gives you with precisely that. There are several people all around the globe that make easy money via these cockfights. If you like earning money quickly, you could consider betting on cockfighting events. These reasons provide gamblers a substantial incentive to wager on cockfighting. [10]

Entertainment Factor Influencing to Cockfight

Cockfighting is a game that has been practiced throughout the Philippine archipelago from the beginning of time. Cockfighting is a combat between two roosters in which one uses a little knife, also known as a spur, affixed to the chicken's leg as a weapon to kill his opponent swiftly if the spur touches his opponent. Cockfighting

is not simply a game of enjoyment for the community in the archipelago; locals feel that rearing roosters may bring economic benefits and be a way to make money during the dry season.

Cockfighting gambling is popular among gambling organizations because the game of cockfighting does not take long to determine the winner. People who wager on cockfighting prefer cockfighting that employs a little knife because cockfighting with a knife spur does not take long to kill its opponent, allowing them to swiftly determine which chicken won. Then there are the typical sorts of fighting chickens, such as Bangkok chicken and Filipino chicken. The ideal Bangkok chicken for use as a fighting chicken has a strong physique and a good mentality, whereas the Filipino chicken has agile movements and a strong punch thanks to its muscular and slender body. Filipino chickens are often referred to as spur fighters due to their agility in injuring their opponents and avoiding attacks. Simply said, impact is a change that happens as a result of an action. These activities might be social, economic, physical, chemical, or biological in nature. In addition, cockfighting games are also a hobby and entertainment not only that from cockfighting games can also make money. Then also from the game of cockfighting which is carried out by some village people, it is very possible to be liked because the game of cockfighting can provide entertainment and spectacle for people who have free time on Sundays, not only that for the rooster entrepreneur from the cockfighting game it provides an income.

Many people like betting on cockfights on a regular basis since it is one of the most exciting forms of gambling available. When wagering on cockfights, entertainment is certain. These battles are really fascinating and entertaining. Many people feel that betting on cockfights is not very profitable and that only win a tiny amount of money. The result of the game determines whether you win or lose the wager. Nowadays, cockfight wagering is conducted on the internet, and it is quite lucrative. People like the fact that these cockfights are more lucrative than other forms of gambling. Thus, Philippines cockfighting is also a way for Filipinos to release the stresses of daily life. But perhaps most importantly, they view it as a chance to make money at a time when employment is scarce. The majority of Filipinos believe in lady luck, easy money, and miracles. In contrast to the harshness of reality, it is the Filipino concept of a romantic existence. [11]

Learning Factor Influencing to Cockfight

Cockfighting is a pastime to a great majority of Filipinos who find infinite fascination in the sport, which has been aptly described as a game of a million thrills. The deadly game brings out good qualities that mold the character of men. The raw courage of the roosters has inspired bravery and perseverance. It could be recalled that the great Napoleon Bonaparte stage cockfights before major battles to inspire his soldiers to emulate the courage, bravery and perseverance of the feathered warriors which taught them to fight to the bitter end at all costs, mindless of victory or defeat. The law of life governs cockfighting which is but an aspect of life itself. Good faith is rewarded with good luck, while bad faith is punished. This is the immutable law of nature enshrined in the laws of men. Cockfighting has also been described as “hazardous to one’s wealth”. One valuable lesson that a cockfight aficionado must learn is the virtue of self-control and self-restraint. This author, a cockfight aficionado all his life, has written this article to share with others the valuable lessons he learned through the years, by way of paying his debt of gratitude to the sport which has brought honor, thrills, joy and benefits, both the tangibles and the intangibles.[12]

There are two types of bets in cock fighting: the central bet contributed by the owners of the two birds at even money, and the side bets from spectators, never at even money. The owner of the victorious bird takes home the entire central bet and the announcement of how much has been staked is of considerable interest to the crowd as it shows the confidence the owners and handlers have in their own roosters. [13]

Challenges of the Police Officers to Suppress Illegal Cockfight

Thirteen people were taken into custody on Sunday in Gapan City, Nueva Ecija, for allegedly participating in illegal gaming. The accused were caught conducting an unlawful cockfight in Barangay Maburak, according to Brig. Gen. Matthew Baccay, director of the Central Luzon police. Some of the suspects attempted to jump into the river and flee, but the raiding team caught them. The operation, according to Baccay, was brought about by a tip from a local who told the police about illegal gaming in their barrio. According to the police, the gamblers were discovered in possession of P2,380 in bet money and three live and one dead fighting cocks. The authorities are currently looking into the kidnapping of 31 cockfight spectators in Manila and Laguna. [14]

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2. METHODS

This research study employed quantitative-descriptive research design using survey method to determine the level of the identified factors influencing the residents to cockfight and the challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfighting in the Municipality of San Francisco (Anao-aon), Surigao del Norte, Philippines. Descriptive research design aimed to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon, and it could answer what, where, and how questions, but not why questions. [15]

The respondents of this study were the 81 selected residents in the Municipality of Anao-aon chosen using the purposive sampling technique which follows the criterion that they must at least engaged to cockfight in the past 12 months. Also, 41 police officers assigned in the municipality who have the experience to arrest illegal gambler in the place were purposefully chosen as respondents.

Researchers-made questionnaire was utilized subjected to validation from experts. Specifically, experts in the field of criminal justice, language, and research were tapped to conduct face and content validation of the survey questionnaires. Questionnaire A was intended for the residents determining the factors influencing them to cockfight, while Questionnaire B was for the police officers determining their challenges in suppressing illegal cockfighting in the community. The researchers approached the respondents personally to explain the study's objectives and distribute questionnaire at their post (police) and homes (residents). The normality assumption was verified, and so, mean, standard deviation, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and Pearson correlation were utilized to analyze and interpret the results of the data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Profile of the Resident-Respondents

Profile Variables	f(n=80)	%
Age		
13-18	4	5.00
19-30	46	57.50
31-40	17	21.25
41-50	9	11.25
51-60	4	5.00
No. of Years playing cockfight		
less than a year	30	37.50
1-2 years	23	28.75
3-5 years	17	21.25
6 years and above	10	12.50
Estimated Monthly Income		
1,000-5,000	50	62.50
6,000-10,000	25	31.25
11,000-15,000	3	3.75
16,000-20,000	2	2.50
Frequency of Playing Cockfight in a month		
Once a month	41	51.25
twice a month	29	36.25
thrice a month	6	7.50
every week	4	5.00
No. of cock or rooster		
less than 5	42	52.50
less than 10	25	31.25
More than 10	13	16.25

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Average Money Spent for Cockfight in a month		
500-1000	67	83.75
1001-1500	4	5.00
1501-2000	8	10.00
2001-2500	1	1.25

Table 1 shows the profile of the participants as to age, sex, number of years playing cockfight, estimated monthly income, frequency of playing cockfight in a month, number of cock and rooster, and average money spent for cockfight in a month. As to age, 46 of the 80 participants belong to age bracket of 19-30 years old; however, four (4) of them belong to the age bracket of 51-60 years old. As to sex, all 80 participants are male. As to number of years playing cockfight, 30 of them played gambling cockfight in less than a year with 37.50 and 10 (12.50) of them played the gambling played for 6 years and above. As to estimated monthly income, 50 of the participants earn 1,000-5,000 with 62.50 and two (2) of them earn 16,000-20,000. As to frequency of playing cockfight in a month, 41 of the participants played cockfight once a month with 51.25 and also four (4) of them admitted that they played the gambling game every week. As to the number of cock or rooster, 42 of the participants revealed that they had less than 5 cock or rooster; however, 13 admitted that they had more than 10 cock or rooster. As to average monthly spent for gambling cockfight in a month. 67 admitted that they gambled for 500-1000 per fight; however, one (1) admitted to spend 2001-2500.

Table 2. Profile of the Police Officers

Profile Variables	f(n=41)	%
Age		
20-30	10	24.39
31-40	12	29.27
41-50	19	46.34
Sex		
Male	34	82.93
Female	7	17.07
Length of Service		
10 years below	22	53.66
20 years below	18	43.90
30 years below	1	2.44
Designation		
Rifleman	9	21.95
WCPD PNCO	1	2.44
Beat Patrol	7	17.07
Investigation PNCO	1	2.44
Station Driver	1	2.44
Supply PNCO	1	2.44
Crime Registrar	1	2.44
Assistant Admin	3	7.32
E-Warrant In-Charge	1	2.44
Eroque In-Charge	2	4.88
Finance PNCO	1	2.44
Operation PNCO	1	2.44
Assistant Investigator	1	2.44
Chief of Police	1	2.44
Admin PNCO	1	2.44
MESPO	1	2.44
Assistant Supply	1	2.44
Subpoena & Warrant Server	1	2.44

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WCPD Investigator	1	2.44
HR PNCO	1	2.44
HRDD PNCO	1	2.44
Assitant Operation	1	2.44
Assistant PCR	1	2.44
PCR PNCO	1	2.44

Table 2 shows the profile of the police officers as to age, sex, length of service, and designation. Of the 41 participants, 19 of them have age bracket of 41-50 with 46.34. However, 10 of them have the age bracket of 20-30 years old with 24.39. As to sex, 34 of the participants were male with 82.93 and seven (7) of them were female with 17.07. As to the length of the service, 22 of them had the length of service of 10 years below with 53.66 and one (1) of the respondents had 30 years below. As to designation, nine (9) of the respondents with 21.95 had their designation of being a rifleman with 21.95; however, 20 of the respondents had different designation.

Table 3. Level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight

Indicators	M	SD	VI	QD
Economic Factor				
1. I play cockfight as my source of income and my way to improve quality of life.	2.70	0.91	A	MH
2. Cockfight provide income which is enough for my basic needs.	2.45	0.73	D	SH
3. I earn easy money in cockfight gambling activity.	2.73	0.78	A	MH
4. This gambling activity is a form of investment for it can double or triple the money.	2.46	0.81	D	SH
5. I can easily provide the financial means to my children to school, house bills and others from playing cockfight activity.	1.53	0.67	SD	L
Average:	2.37	0.78	D	SH
Entertainment Factor				
1. I find pleasure when I watch the actual cockfight game.	3.19	0.73	A	MH
2. I change negative to positive mood when I join in cockfight game.	3.19	0.80	A	MH
3. The game arouses my interest to apply strategies in order to win.	3.23	0.66	A	MH
4. The game provides genuine happiness every time my cock wins.	3.48	0.62	SA	VH
5. The games serves as my stress reliever everytime I watch and play cockfight.	3.38	0.66	SA	VH
Average:	3.29	0.69	SA	VH
Learning Factor				
1. The game helps develop my critical thinking of applying different strategies.	3.20	0.80	A	MH
2. Winning strategies are factors which I learned in playing this gambling activity.	3.29	0.78	SA	VH
3. Learning every process of this gambling activity builds up my character as a person.	3.14	1.02	A	MH
4. Every win of my bird boosts my confidence to invest and continue the game.	3.41	0.76	SA	VH
5. When I am inside the gambling place, I learn a lot from the stories of every player regardless they win or lose.	3.28	0.80	SA	VH
Average:	3.26	0.83	SA	VH
General Average:	2.98	0.77	A	MH

Legend: SA- Strongly Agree, A-Agree, D-Disagree, SD-Strongly Disagree, VH-Very High, MH-Moderately High, SH-Slightly High, L-Low

Table 3 shows the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight. As to economic factor, the residents observed that the that they played cockfight as their source of income with and their way to improve quality of life with the mean of 2.70 and standard deviation of 0.91. This means that this gambling game becomes the source of livelihood of some of the residents. They also observed that this gambling activity provide easy money for them with the mean of 2.73 and standard deviation of 0.78. This means that this gambling activity was one of the ways for them to earn for a living. However, they less observed that this gambling activity was insufficient to their basic needs with the mean of 2.45 and standard deviation 0.73 and they less observed that this gambling activity was a form of investment that could double or triple the money with the mean of 2.46 and standard deviation of 0.81.

The implications of the data revealed that even most of the residents earned 1,000-5,000 a month, they played cockfight once a month for this somehow served as the source of income and their way to improve their life. Though they spent 500- 1000 for cockfight in a month, they believed that this gambling activity would give easy money to provide their family basic needs.

As to entertainment factor, the residents were highly observed that playing the gambling game provides the genuine happiness everytime their cock wins with the mean 3.48 and standard deviation of 0.62. Another, they admitted that they highly observed that the game serves as their stress reliever everytime they watched and played cockfight with the mean of 3.38 and standard deviation of 0.66.

However, they only observed that the game aroused their interest to apply strategies in order to win with the mean of 3.23 and standard deviation of 0.66. Also, they claimed that playing or joining the gambling game changed their mood from negative to positive with the mean 3.19 and standard deviation 0.80 and they admitted that they find pleasure when they watched the actual cockfight game with the mean of 3.19 and standard deviation of 0.73.

The implications revealed that because the gambling players experienced winning the game for many times though they played less than a year which aroused the interests of the residents for this gave them genuine happiness. Majority of the residents played cockfighting activity aged 19-30 years old for this was their stress reliever everytime they watched and played cockfighting activity.

As to learning factor, the residents accepted that everytime their cock wins, they boosted their confidence to invest and continue the game with the mean of 3.41 and standard deviation of 0.76. Additionally, they implied that the winning strategies were the factors which they learned in playing the gambling game with the mean of 3.29 and standard deviation of 0.78 and also when they were inside the gambling place, they learned a lot of stories from of every player regardless they win or lose with the mean of 3.28 and standard deviation of 0.80. However, they only observed that the game helped them develop their critical thinking by applying different strategies with the mean of 3.20 and standard deviation of 0.80 and also they observed that by learning every process of this gambling activity of this gambling activity builds up the character as a person.

The implications of study revealed that everytime the residents played the cockfight gambling activity for majority of them played once a month, they applied winning strategies to ensure their cock wins. Through this, they players boosted their confidence to invest more money even if their estimated monthly income ranging from 5,000 below. They believed that they earned more money if they invested more. They hooked to the game for they heard a lot of winning stories which motivated them to play the game.

Accordingly, Cockfighting, which has been correctly described as "a game of a million thrills," is a popular pastime for Filipinos, who are intrigued by the sport, which brings out the best in men's characters. Bravery and perseverance have been encouraged by the roosters' unrestrained audacity [12]. It's vital to remember that Napoleon Bonaparte hosted cockfights before significant battles to inspire his soldiers to model the valor, bravery, and tenacity of the feathered warriors, who taught them to fight to the last end at all costs, regardless of win or defeat. The law of life, which is merely one aspect of life, governs cockfighting. While poor faith results in punishment, good faith brings good fortune.

Table 4. Extent of the challenges of Police Officers in suppressing illegal cockfight

Challenges	M	SD	VI	QD
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1. The culture of the Filipinos to think this gambling activity is just a simple game which challenges us to arrest both cock players and the watchers.	1.32	0.61	SD	NC
2. The exact location of the gambling hall or activity is one of the challenges of every police assigned for this is done secretly.	3.44	0.55	SA	HC
3. Cooperation among the residents is one of the difficulties that the police assigned is facing.	3.59	0.67	SA	HC
4. Charges and penalties of this illegal gambling are bailable so people are not afraid to assemble and invite players and watchers.	3.27	0.55	SA	HC
5. Political support of this illegal gambling is one of the hindrances in arresting both the players and the watchers.	3.41	0.71	SA	HC
6. Cock fight gambling activity usually played at the remote areas or at the top mountains which challenges us to arrest the gamblers.	3.56	0.55	SA	HC
7. There should be at least one gambler arrested when there is an alleged report of illegal cock fighting activity in the area.	3.24	0.49	A	MC
Average	3.12	0.59	A	MC

Legend: SA- Strongly Agree, A-Agree SD- Strongly Disagree, HC-Highly Challenged, MC-Moderately Challenged, NC-Not Challenged

Table 4 shows the extent of the challenges of Police Officers in suppressing illegal cockfight. The 41 police officers designated in the Municipality of San Francisco Anao-aon Surigao del Norte admitted that they highly observed that the cooperation among the residents is one of the difficulties they faced with the mean of 3.59 and standard deviation of 0.67. They observed that during the operation, there should be at least one cock player arrested when there was arrest operation in the area with the mean of 3.12 and standard deviation of 0.59. However, they did not observe and consider that the culture of the Filipinos of the gambling activity is just a simple game which challenges them when they arrest cock players and watchers with the mean of 1.32 and standard deviation of 0.61. This clearly implies that the police officers in the Municipality of San Francisco Anao-aon strongly affirm that cockfight activities are not just only a simple game to the residents but a form of gambling activity because it involves money as their bit of exchange whether win or lose in a cock fight. For the residents, it is a big deal for some this is their source of income and beneficial to their families.

Table 5. Significant difference on the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight based on profile

Profile	Factors	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	Economic Factor	0.672	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Entertainment Factor	0.081	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Learning Factor	0.537	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
No. of Years playing cockfight	Economic Factor	0.707	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Entertainment Factor	0.256	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Learning Factor	0.284	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Estimated Monthly Income	Economic Factor	0.006	Reject null hypothesis	Significant
	Entertainment Factor	0.130	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Frequency of Playing Cockfight in a month	Learning Factor	0.003	Reject null hypothesis	Significant
	Economic Factor	0.705	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant

	Entertainment Factor	0.928	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Learning Factor	0.704	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Economic Factor	0.528	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
No. of cock or rooster	Entertainment Factor	0.467	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Learning Factor	0.354	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Economic Factor	0.054	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Average Money Spent for Cockfight in a month	Entertainment Factor	0.438	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
	Learning Factor	0.141	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant

Table 5 shows the significant difference on the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight when grouped by profile. There were no significant differences on the economic factor, entertainment factor, and learning factor when grouped by age, number of years playing cockfight, frequency of playing cockfight in a month, number of cock or rooster, and the average money spent for cockfight in a month. Also, there were no significant differences on entertainment factor when grouped by estimated monthly income. However, there are significant differences on the level of economic factor and learning factor that influence the residents to cockfight when grouped according to their estimated monthly income.

The implications revealed that the residents had different monthly incomes and the majority earned below 10,000-5,000. Because they differ in terms of monthly income, their money spent on this gambling activity also differs which constitutes their income every time they won the game. They had different learning experiences because those with higher incomes, they could sustain from playing the game and the tendency was they were more exposed to playing the game. The more they played the game, the more they won and the more they learned.

Table 6. Significant difference on the level of the challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfight based on profile

Profile	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	0.030	Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Sex	0.235	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.704	Do not reject null hypothesis	Not Significant
Designation	0.005	Reject null hypothesis	Significant

Table 6 shows the significant difference in the level of the challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfighting. There were no significant differences in the challenges of the Police Officers in suppressing the illegal cockfight when grouped by sex and length of service. However, there were significant differences in the challenges experienced by the police officers in suppressing the illegal cockfight when they are grouped by age and designation.

The implications of the study revealed that those police officers aged 41-50 experienced more challenges in suppressing cockfighting than those 40 years old below for this group age were more exposed to arrest cockfighting players in the operation. Additionally, the municipality Anao-aon is a rural area and mountainous. This location greatly contribute to more challenges in the operation for several cockfighting activities were conducted in the mountains which is a factor that may significantly contributed to challenges. Although there were stationed police officers in Anao-aon, majority of them assigned to different job positions, and only few were assigned to conduct cockfight operation.

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Table 7. Significant relationship between the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight and the extent of the challenges of Police Officers in suppressing illegal cockfight

Variables	r	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Factors influencing the residents to cockfight and Challenges of police officers in suppressing illegal cockfight	0.35	0.027	Reject null hypothesis	Significant Positive Relationship

Table 7 shows the significant relationship between the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight and the extent of the challenges of Police Officers in suppressing illegal Cockfight. With the p-value of 0.027 and correlation coefficient of 0.35, there was a significant positive relationship between the level of the factors influencing the residents to cockfight and the extent of challenges of Police Officers in suppressing the illegal cockfight. This clearly shows that the three (3) factors are the reasons of why the residents of San Francisco Anao-aon will never stop playing the illegal cock fight activity. Thus, the economic, entertainment, and learning factors which beneficial to residents are contributory factors that challenged the Police Officers to suppress this illegal activity.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study revealed that the economic, entertainment, and learning factors were the driving factors that motivate residents to continue playing the gambling activity. The cockfighting gambling activity became their source of income and provide their family's basic needs. This also entertained them to watch the cockfight for this gambling activity changed their moods from negative to positive, and helped them critically apply strategies to win the game. For the residents, the gambling activity improved their character and critical thinking of applying best strategies from learning different stories. These reasons strongly contributed to challenges of the police officers in suppressing cockfighting for the residents were not cooperative thinking that police operations would lose their income. So, they conducted the gambling activity in the mountains where inaccessible to the police officers, and some of the gambling players had connections to the government and charges once arrested was billable.

Hence, it is recommended that the police officers may consider to educate the residents that playing cockfight is unlawful and that would bring them to jail with corresponding penalties once arrested. Being the implementer of the law, they may consider to host a symposium activity that would educate and bring awareness to the residents on the provisions of the law. The police officers may also partner with the local government unit to plan for a livelihood program that would help the cockfight players or residents to stop the illegal gambling game and focus on the livelihood program that would generate income to the locals. Through this, residents would have the option on their source of income which is not illegal. Furthermore, the police officers may coordinate or partner with the municipal and barangay officials for the strict implementation of the law to stop cockfighting gambling activity in the locality. For future researchers, the scope of the research may be expanded to other municipalities or barangays so Police Officers would be given data on the specific location of the gambling activity.

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